

Outlooks for zeolite catalysts in a low-carbon scenario[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Zeolites today are a unique and highly successful class of catalytic materials, but their role in future low-carbon scenarios comes into question. This perspective article summarises the authors' joint view on zeolite chemistry's future direction for catalytic applications to stimulate discussion identifying pillars on which the scientific community should focus. Particular challenges discussed here include i) our view of the zeolite synthesis focused on new structures with optimised textural properties and design of zeolite catalysts with precise control of the location of active sites; ii) discussion of current, mostly new industrial, requests for zeolitic catalysts; iii) emerging catalytic applications in which zeolites should play a key role; and last but not least iv) opportunities for new types of microporous solids. Although some of these are rather challenging, with many barriers to overcome, we suggest fostering research on these directions as the key to maintaining the crucial role of zeolite as catalysts. Discussion on the future role of zeolite science and technology is organised in consideration of three possible future scenarios: (i) a low-carbon BAU (business-as-usual) scenario and (ii) two advanced scenarios, which differ in terms of the degree of circularity (low and high, LC and HC respectively), and (iii) level of substitution of fossil fuels with alternative energy and carbon sources. Trends characterising these scenarios and their impact on zeolite science and technology are discussed to provide the readers with the elements, tools and clues to identify priorities in research and application of zeolite catalysts.

1. Introduction

Zeolites are an important class of catalytic materials, playing a crucial role in many processes, including oil refining, petrochemistry, biomass transformation, and environmental applications [1–9]. In addition, these materials find many other important applications, from separation, filtration, storage and cleaning to more exotic uses such as in electronics and nanomedicine [10–12]. The main features making zeolites unique as catalytic materials are that they offer the following:

1. well-ordered porous structures that can be tuned in great detail by modern synthetic methods;
2. control with great precision the position, environment and nature of active centres (acid-base, redox sites or other);
3. space confinement (guest-host interaction) imposing a unique influence on reaction pathways;

4. the possibility to realise spatially-controlled multifunctional catalysis;
5. a high level of molecular-level understanding, for example, by theoretical modelling and, from the application perspective, the possibility for an ad-hoc design;
6. scalability to tons synthesis.

In addition, zeolites often have better resource efficiency (waste/CO₂ production, selectivity) and conversion performances than other catalysts [13].

The success of zeolites as catalytic materials has stimulated research and discovery of new mesoporous materials as well as a large variety of other ordered porous materials, from porous materials having covalent organic frameworks (COFs), hydrogen-bonded organic frameworks (HOFs) and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), to inorganic-organic hybrids, controlled layered materials, hierarchically ordered porous

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materials, ordered porous carbon materials and many others [11,14,15]. Research has largely expanded from the early efforts on silico-alumina zeolitic materials to include i) a large variety of ordered porous structures, ii) methods for controlling the nature and location of active centres, iii) the development of structurally equivalent organic or hybrid structures with modular assembly characteristics, iv) preparation of hierarchically organised materials, and v) controlled bidimensional materials. The uses have grown from initial fossil-fuel refinery applications to include petrochemical processes, biomass conversion, many environmentally relevant applications (from automotive to control of greenhouse gas and pollutants emissions) and waste valorisation such as plastic conversion. Thus, zeolite catalysts are one of the most versatile and successful types of catalysis, bringing many societal benefits and great improvement in catalytic science [6,16–21]. However, notwithstanding the large variety of materials developed with ordered porous structures, industrial catalytic materials are still dominated by just a few zeolites (only about 5–10 are those of major industrial relevance) [12, 22].

Despite many important advances, the future of this area of catalysis comes under question as we go through the energy transition. The energy transition, which affects both refinery and chemical production, will also impose many changes on production modes and the use of raw resources. As fossil fuel usage progressively declines, some of today's crucial technologies using zeolite catalysts, such as fluid catalytic cracking, will have to adapt or die, especially due to changes in demand for gasoline and diesel for (light) motor vehicles. The European Union aims by 2035 to limit the manufacture of new light road transport vehicles using conventional internal combustion systems and eventually limit their use to e-fuels, excluding biofuels (although the use of biofuels is still a matter of big debate) [23]. Without producing (or by severely limiting) gasoline and diesel production, the current economics of refineries will no longer be sustainable. At the same time, chemical production will likely follow an analogous deep transition, with the introduction of novel technologies, largely different from the past, and where the role of zeolite-based catalysts is, as yet, unclear.

Accordingly, the design of zeolitic catalysts should adapt to this new challenging framework. Hence, they could play a more relevant role in topics related to the production and transformation of hydrogen and other energy vectors, like ammonia, alcohols, DME and formic acid [24] and the development of sustainable jet and marine e-fuel [25]. Zeolite catalysts are expected to contribute to several strategic processes, such as CO₂ hydrogenation, alcohols/glycerol/bio-oil steam reforming, methane and ammonia decomposition, platform chemicals C-C coupling, alcohol dehydration/olefin oligomerisation and triglycerides hydro-conversion, amongst others [26,27].

Undoubtedly many relevant advances have been made in zeolitic catalysts in terms of optimising their design to maximise catalytic performance, precise control of their properties in terms of crystallinity/structure, accessibility (nano-, hierarchical- and 2D zeolites), creation of multifunctionality (Brønsted/Lewis acidity and incorporation of metallic components) and to achieve longer lifetimes [28–30]. However, the question is whether we can apply the current large body of knowledge without significant methodological changes to these new fields or, instead, whether the new areas of catalytic use require us to rethink the way the design of zeolitic catalysts has to be addressed [31–33].

A major transition has already occurred in the last one-two decade with the introduction of bio-based processes, even if few are commercially used today, mainly for cost or infrastructural reasons. Several of these processes involve zeolitic catalysts [1,4,6,26,34–37]. However, their development is often an extension of existing zeolitic materials and concepts used in converting fossil fuel-derived platform molecules, notwithstanding the differences in the substrates [31]. In other words, continuity in the science and technology of zeolites can be identified in their expanding range of use. Addressing the new challenges of the transition to a sustainable, net-zero-emission (NZE) future requires a more disruptive approach in the zeolitic area [38], even if this

development is still based on the large body of existing knowledge. However, this question is rarely addressed in the literature, which usually does not differentiate in terms of design requirements for zeolites for converting biomass or fuel cell applications, for example [20].

Discussing the role of zeolites in a sustainable, low-carbon future cannot leave aside that many factors, difficult to predict, will determine the future and thus, a productive discussion has to be linked to possible/probable scenarios and, at the same time, take into consideration that many processes currently in place will almost certainly continue to exist. Thus, they must maintain current efficiency while adapting to the changing future landscape.

In summary, the current status of zeolites is that they have been a success story in the science and technology of catalysis. However, the changing scenario for energy and chemistry put a question mark on the current main areas of use of zeolites as catalysts (refining, petrochemical and environmental).

Zeolites offer many opportunities and advances for heterogeneous catalysts: precise control of the structure and porosity, controlled location of active sites, and more. However, a deep transition is occurring. Analyzing and discussing their role in future sustainable, low-carbon, energy and chemical production scenarios is thus necessary. Their role may be different depending on which transformative scenario plays out.

For this reason, zeolite's advantages and limitations concerning future scenarios should first be recapped to discuss how zeolite science should expand to take full advantage of their potentialities. The following section provides indications to stimulate discussion in academic and industrial research. The directions outlined are highly challenging. Their translation into reality may be difficult. For example, the control at the atomic level of the incorporation of heteroatoms in specific crystallographic sites is difficult to verify experimentally. The synthesis of new zeolitic structures with the desired porous architecture is an objective that has been pursued for some time with scientifically relevant results but still limited applicability. Nevertheless, the advances in these areas, e.g., the precise control of the localisation of the active sites and a tailored porous architecture, are more significant for zeolites than other catalytic materials. The control of these characteristics is crucial to develop the catalysts for the future sustainable scenario. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight these aspects because they are crucial elements to strengthen the role and impact of zeolite science and technology in implementing future scenarios.

2. Advances and challenges in the fundamental understanding

2.1. Precise synthesis and control of location and type of acid sites

Even though zeolites are one of the most important classes of heterogeneous catalysts from the industrial perspective, key challenges still exist that could substantially enhance zeolites' impact in catalysis. These challenges can be divided into three categories: i) chemical, ii) structural, and iii) textural.

From the chemical point of view, we cannot completely control the chemical composition of zeolites in the full possible range. No single zeolite can be synthesised from Si/Al molar ratio equal to 1 (the lowest limit given by Loewenstein's rule) up to infinity. Most synthesized zeolites can be prepared within a specific limited Si/Al range. The Si/Al ratio may be modified via post-synthesis treatments, but this invariably (for good or for ill) also changes other characteristics of the zeolite. Despite significant effort, zeolite FAU with a framework Si/Al ratio > 6–7 cannot be directly synthesised. The situation is even more complex in the case of catalytically important framework heteroatoms (M) such as tetravalent Ti or Sn and trivalent Ga or Fe [39]. Framework Si/M molar ratios usually exhibit higher values or narrower ranges for Si/M ratios than Si/Al. While the incorporation of heteroatoms into zeolite frameworks is a rather difficult challenge, the determination of the exact location of these heteroatoms in the zeolite structure is even more complicated due to the similarity of Al to Si in the case of aluminosilicate

zeolites or low concentration of heteroatoms and the presence of multiple crystallographic sites in the zeolite framework. Despite these challenges, there are some successful reports on determining the location of heteroatoms in zeolite structures [40], even the difficulties in proving the localization.

Considering structural challenges in zeolite synthesis, there exists the so-called "zeolite conundrum" – why more than a million zeolite structures have been predicted, while the number of those synthesised and approved by the Structural Committee of IZA is only about 250. In addition, synthesised zeolites almost exclusively lay on the so-called "Traditional Synthesis Vector" line in the energy-density plot proposed by Li and Deem [40]. We struggle to prepare zeolites, which are less energetically favoured. These authors predicted that odd-ring structures are rather frequently predicted but not-yet synthesised zeolites, while in existing structures, the odd-rings larger than 7 are still rather rare despite some recent advances [41–44].

From the textural point of view, zeolites are usually prepared as three-dimensional crystals. However, recently it has been shown that about 15–20 different zeolites can be prepared as two-dimensional (2D) crystals with a thickness of about 1–3 nm (also called nanolayered or nanosheets) [45–47]. This significantly expands our vision of zeolites and provides us with new tools to help control the activity and selectivity of catalytic reactions. Research focus in this area is mostly directed toward industrially important zeolites, like MFI or MWW. Synthesis of 2D MFI zeolites and their self-pillared analogues or nanosponges were recently reported [48–50]. Roth and coworkers' exfoliation of 2D MFI zeolite has also been successful as an extension of this research [45,51]. On the other hand, MWW zeolite represents a zeolitic structure with several different textural analogues (MCM-22, MCM-36, MCM-56, etc.) [46,51–54].

Successful application of zeolites in various industrial catalytic processes is largely based on two critical zeolite properties, i) the zeolite structure containing micropores (often interconnecting) of precisely defined sizes and shapes comparable with the kinetic diameters of specific organic molecules, and ii) the presence of aluminium or other heteroatoms providing zeolites with acidic functionality [55,56]. Both of these parameters will be discussed in this section. The appropriate combination of the size (shape) of zeolite micropores and the optimum location of active sites in framework positions ensures high catalytic activity and selectivity for transforming organic compounds [57].

From the structural point of view, zeolites are usually categorised by the number of tetrahedral "T" atoms (Si, Al, Fe, Ge, etc.) forming entrance windows to the micropore systems: 8-ring (small pore), 10-ring (medium pore), 12-ring (large pore) and larger than 14-ring (extra-large pore) zeolites. These channels are organised in the structure of zeolites as uni-dimensional (not intersecting), two-dimensional (intersecting in one crystallographic plane), or three-dimensional. In addition, some zeolites possess channels of more than one size or contain larger cavities at channel intersections [28]. Fig. 1 depicts schematic images of the

structures LTA (small-pore zeolite), BEC (large-pore zeolite), and FER (combination of small- and medium-pore zeolites) with an indication of crystallographically different T sites in the framework [58–60].

The size and shape of zeolite pores determine the so-called shape selectivity (or molecular sieving), e.g., allowing or rejecting molecules access to or permitting and restricting transition states within the zeolite micropore system [61–63]. While we can determine the location of acid sites in different types of channels [64], e.g. using base probe molecules of different sizes, precise design and control of acid sites specifically at these locations have not yet been achieved.

It is clear that for zeolites differing in the crystal structure, the number of crystallographically different T-sites increases with decreasing symmetry of the crystal structure [65–69]. Regarding industrially highly relevant MFI zeolite, 12 and 24 crystallographically distinguishable T-sites have been recognised for structures with symmetry of $Pnma$ and $P21/n$, respectively. Precise determination of the location of heteroatoms in different crystallographic sites is still rather limited due to i) the usually low concentration of heteroatoms in the framework, ii) their distribution in different crystallographic sites, and iii) in the case of Al due to a similarity to Si preventing selection of the location using current experimental techniques. In some cases, like with Fe, the location of framework Fe has been determined in MFI zeolite using HR-TEM, but this is still an exceptional case [70]. The successful determination of the location of Fe atoms in the MFI zeolite framework creates the possibility of locating other heteroatoms, such as Ti, Sn, or Zr, in zeolite structures if they are present at high enough concentrations within the framework.

New synthesis methods for selectively inserting heteroatoms into desired crystallographic sites, together with new experimental tools that determine their location, are more than needed. A recent review by Yu et al. summarises current state-of-the-art Al chemistry in zeolites, discussing our ability to incorporate Al into zeolite frameworks, modify Si/Al ratios in different zeolites, and highlight some examples of the impact on catalytic performance [40].

Template-free zeolite synthesis does not need to burn off organic structure-directing agents post-synthesis. However, at the moment, the number of zeolites that can be prepared without organic templates is still very limited (MFI, FAU, FER, CHA, RHO, LTA, and MOR). In addition, template-free synthesis also has some disadvantages that may outweigh this advantage, namely, prolongation of the synthesis time, usually higher synthesis temperature, the necessity to use higher amounts of seeds and limitations to the range of possible Si/Al ratios in the case of MFI zeolite. Further, zeolite synthesis in purely inorganic systems can also lead to undesirable crystal morphology and the formation of quartz or cristobalite byproducts. However, some successful examples can be found in recent literature [71–73]. More effort in template-free zeolite synthesis is required.

Despite the complexity of determining Al atoms' location in zeolites, there have been numerous attempts to control it [64,74–78]. Both

Fig. 1. Schematic structures of zeolites LTA, BEC, and FER with examples of crystallographically different T sites in the frameworks (coloured spheres).

inorganic and organic (organic structure-directing agents) cations can influence the Al distribution in zeolite frameworks. In particular, Al species are proposed to be located close to cationic sites that balance their positive charge. Okubo and his coworkers showed that Al could be preferentially incorporated into different T-sites of zeolite IFR when changing the organic structure-directing agent [79]. An indirect method was used to distinguish Al and Si sites within the zeolite framework based on HR-TEM investigations of Mo-modified zeolites due to the strong interaction of Mo with Al [80].

Other approaches for insertion of heteroatoms into particular positions within zeolite frameworks are based on (1) synthesis of zeolites with specific defect(s) and missing atoms [81] or (2) selective removal of a less strongly bound element from the framework and its subsequent replacement (reinsertion) by a catalytically active heteroatom in the free T-position generated. Zeolite SSZ-74 synthesised by Zones et al. is an example of the first approach [82]. Structural analysis of this zeolite revealed that one of the 24 different crystallographic sites is vacant. This presents the opportunity to incorporate heteroatoms into the vacant T-positions of the all-silica SSZ-74 framework, resulting in a zeolite with all heteroatoms in a crystallographically identical site. The second approach has been demonstrated by synthesising borosilicate or germanosilicate zeolites [83,84], where B or Ge can selectively be removed, and heteroatoms reinserted into the framework vacancy sites produced. In the case of B, SSZ-55, SSZ-70, SSZ-33, and SSZ-42 have been prepared as crystalline borosilicates, deboronated and then Al-inserted to generate a new type of zeolite [85,86]. Recent findings show that deboronation treatment of zeolite B-SSZ-55 does not generate vacancy defects consisting of four silanol groups (silanol nests) but rather creates vacancies consisting of only two silanol groups (silanol dyads). They derive by the silanol condensation of two silanol groups at the silanol dyads, which is relevant in introducing Al atoms [87].

Modifying germanosilicate zeolites offers exciting possibilities taking advantage of the reinsertion approach [56,88,89]. Several germanosilicate zeolites, e.g. UTL, consist of silica layers connected by d4r (double-four-ring) units, in which Ge is highly preferentially located. When more than 4 Ge atoms are in each d4r, the zeolite can be hydrolysed to form individual loosely bound layers connected only by relatively weak hydrogen bonds. This hydrolysis is the "Disassembly" step of the ADOR (Assembly – Disassembly – Organisation – Reassembly) mechanism [90], which is highly useful in the synthesis of novel zeolites and their precursors (IWV to IPC-20, UOV to IPC-12, ITH, ITR) [91–93]. However, hydrolysis can still proceed when there are less than four atoms of Ge in each d4r. The silica layers remain interconnected, and defects (missing T-atoms) are specifically formed in d4r units (see Fig. 2). These defects can be "healed" by inserting heteroatoms, which will be located specifically within d4r units, which are highly accessible for reactants while preserving the original zeolite structure. This approach could demonstrate that direct synthesis and post-synthesis methods should be considered for preparing zeolite catalysts with heteroatoms in particular crystallographic sites.

2.2. Opportunities for new types and textures of zeolites

Only about ten different structural types of zeolites are currently used in industrial catalysis, and the latest one was introduced more than 25 years ago. Those include MFI, FAU, MWW and BEA, among the most relevant. An important question arises – do we need zeolites with other structural parameters or textural properties to efficiently run existing industrial processes or to accommodate new emerging reactions? There is no doubt that there is intensive research in this area in different directions, and many promising results have been achieved; some are highlighted here.

One of the most characteristic structural features of zeolites that have successfully been utilised in catalysis is their shape selectivity, allowing us to control the product distribution of reactions. Para-selective transformations, including para-dialkyl-aromatics formation, are an important example [94]. The size of the entrance windows to the zeolite channel system controls molecular entrance/exit; the size/shape of channels and intersections restricts transition state geometry at the active sites. In many emerging applications, feedstocks are likely to become larger and bulkier. Thus, successful synthesis and application of extra-large pore zeolites would be highly beneficial. However, research has not synthesised "stable" and cost-effective extra-large pore zeolites. These often contain Ge, which is costly, and Ge-O bonds are easy to hydrolysed, leading to lower stability, especially if some regeneration is required to remove "coke". Therefore, synthesising extra-large pore aluminosilicate zeolites is still an important goal in zeolite synthesis.

Transformation of bulkier substrates using zeolite catalysts is important not only for bulkier feedstocks but also for forming bulkier products (e.g. pharmaceuticals, flavours, fragrances). Usually, the synthesis occurs under milder conditions than converting bulk feedstocks, and catalysts are not regenerated or recovered for reuse after synthesising high-value products. Thus, the stability of zeolites may be less critical in this case. Whether we need extra-large pore zeolites for such reactions, usually involving condensation and other pathways, should be confirmed. Are confinement effects important, or do we need zeolitic active (acid) sites located at external surface sites of zeolite crystals? In this case, we could utilise an increasing number of so-called two-dimensional (2D) zeolites, also called nanosheets or nanolayered zeolites. 2D zeolites usually have a layer thickness of around 1–3 nm, while the size in the plane of the layers is in the tens to hundreds nm range [45, 95].

There are two fundamental approaches to synthesising 2D zeolites, bottom-up and top-down. Bottom-up synthesis of the zeolites is well established and recognised due to differences in X-ray diffraction patterns of as-synthesised zeolites and their calcined forms. ERB-1, synthesised by Millini et al. [96], was the first known example of a layered zeolite, the structure of which belongs to the MWW type. In due course, other 2D zeolites were discovered, forming the group of about 20 2D zeolites of different structures and compositions known today. A particular example of the bottom-up approach is the synthesis of 2D MFI zeolite. Ryoo et al. [48,97] synthesised this layered zeolite using a

Fig. 2. Replacement of Ge from the structure of UTL for Al to generate Brønsted acidity in Ge-poor UTL.

specially designed template which inhibits crystal growth in one direction due to long hydrocarbon chains. In principle, most zeolites could be synthesised in 2D forms, and their layered structures could bring new benefits to zeolite-catalysed reactions. Usually, 2D zeolites exhibit high resistance to deactivation via coking. However, shape selectivity is generally lower due to significantly shorter diffusion paths within zeolite channels or between zeolite layers [28].

The top-down approach is briefly touched on *vide supra* when discussing the hydrolysis of germano-silicates and the ADOR mechanism. Hydrolysis of Ge-rich zeolites leads to the complete separation of the silicate layers with the preservation of their structure (Fig. 3). These layers can be used as catalysts or supports for active catalysts, benefiting from their large surface areas. Incorporations of acid or metal sites can also be realized with this approach. Thus, those layered materials can be used for different reactions, including cascade syntheses. In addition, Veselý described the possibility of reconstructing the original UTL zeolite from IPC-1 P layers utilising bridging Al atoms to generate Brønsted acid sites [98]. Therefore, after functionalisation, the IPC-1 P layers can be used as catalysts or as a building block for new zeolites. While the reconstruction of the original UTL structure has successfully been achieved, the enlargement of pore sizes starting from IPC-1 P layers remains a huge challenge. 2D zeolites bring new opportunities for creating new zeolites and highly active catalysts. Likely they will shortly find application in the chemicals industry.

Another alternative for improving the accessibility of zeolites is the development of materials with a hierarchical porosity [99–103]. The so-called hierarchical zeolites combine different size ranges of well-defined porosity, so in addition to the zeolitic micropores inherent to each crystal structure, these materials also exhibit larger pores; most frequently, hierarchical zeolites have micro- and mesopores. However, the additional porosity may sometimes lie in the super-micro or macropore ranges. Likewise, the synthesis of hierarchical zeolites with a trimodal pore size distribution, encompassing at the same time micro-, meso- and macro-pores, has been reported [104–106].

Hierarchical porosity provokes drastic changes in the zeolite features and, therefore, in their application as catalysts [107–110]. Textural properties, e.g. BET surface area and pore volumes, are generally improved, leading to enhanced properties such as diffusion. The share of micro- and mesoporosities usually show opposite trends, with lowering both surface area and micropore volume as the contribution from mesopores increases. This is expected because the mesopore/external surface area is created at the expense of the micropore one [99,100]. Hierarchical zeolites have been prepared with total mesopore/external areas in the range of 100 – 400 m²/g, representing a huge variation compared to the practically negligible value of this parameter in unmodified conventional micron-size zeolites. This opens-up the possibility of using zeolites as catalysts for converting much bulkier molecules, even if their size is too large to enter zeolitic micropores. Thus, hierarchical zeolites have been claimed to enhance performance in a large variety of fine chemistry reactions [111,112] or the conversion of

polymeric substrates [113], such as catalytic pyrolysis of biomass [114] and catalytic cracking of polyolefin plastic wastes [115,116], due to their lower steric hindrances and/or improved diffusional characteristics in comparison with conventional zeolites.

Another important effect derived from introducing additional meso- or macro-pores in zeolites is the reduction of the effective path-length in intracrystalline diffusional pathways [109]. This can improve the overall diffusion rate, decreasing the Thiele modulus and thus significantly enhancing the share of the crystals participating effectively in the catalytic process (i.e., effectiveness factors approaching the one value). However, the experimental measurement of the intracrystalline diffusion rate (through parameters like the diffusional time constant or the effective diffusion coefficient) is not straightforward due to the existence of a high number of techniques that very often provide contradictory results or are performed under operation conditions quite different from those present in the catalytic tests [117–119]. This is the case of the temperature despite being a variable that strongly affects the diffusion, the reaction rates and mechanisms. Moreover, the possible role of the external surface, as an additional barrier or for facilitating surface diffusion, in the overall transport phenomena is still unclear [120]. Another point to consider is that small changes in the effective size of the micropores may have a strong effect on the coefficient diffusion values with variations about several magnitude orders. Connectivity between mesopores or between mesopores and micropores is another issue to be considered when assessing the overall diffusion rate [121]. Hence the quality of the hierarchical porosity is linked to the degree of connectivity.

Facilitated diffusion affects reactants moving into the interior part of zeolite crystals and favours the products exiting the micropore system. In addition, improved porosity has an important impact on zeolite deactivation by coke formation by helping avoid the negative effects of micropore blockage caused by the accumulation of carbonaceous matter [122,123]. A typical case of the positive effects of hierarchical porosity in zeolites on retarding their deactivation by coke deposition is methanol conversion over ZSM-5 zeolite [124]. However, how catalyst regeneration by air combustion at relatively high temperatures affects the hierarchical porosity has not been reported extensively in the open literature, despite being a crucial aspect of using zeolite catalysts. Catalytic studies of hierarchical zeolites need to take into account appropriate catalyst equilibration.

Equilibration by hydrothermal regeneration (e.g., steaming the catalyst) often creates intrinsic hierarchical porosity within the zeolite (e.g., as a consequence of dealumination) that may raise baseline performance. Hierarchical porosity built into fresh zeolite crystals may not survive such equilibration, so their stability should be evaluated before catalytic improvements can be claimed. Conclusions made on studies on “fresh” (unequilibrated) hierarchical zeolites should be taken with a pinch of salt. In addition, in industrial catalysts, zeolites are generally incorporated into formed catalyst particles with hierarchical porosity deliberately built into them to improve accessibility and diffusion into

Fig. 3. Replacement of Ge from the structure of UTL for Al hydrolyse (disassembly) Ge-rich UTL into layered IPC-1 P material (bottom). On the right: Transmission electron microscopy image of IPC-1 P.

and out of the catalyst particles (as practised for over 100 years in industrial catalysts).

Furthermore, excessive fresh hierarchical porosity can reduce the hydrothermal stability of zeolite crystals themselves, thereby leading to more rapid permanent catalyst deactivation by crystalline structure loss over time. Specific results on these aspects are often neglected or absent in the open literature, and even companies promoting hierarchical zeolites do not always prove these aspects adequately. It may be worth remarking that from an industrial perspective, an improved zeolite catalyst should be assessed from multiple aspects: (i) the additional cost for the preparation, (ii) the catalytic properties after having equilibrated/aged properly, (iii) other properties relevant for industrial operations, such as mechanical and physical ones (a hierarchical structure can soften particles, and lower density too much). Validation of the benefits of hierarchical porosity requires properly equilibrated catalysts tested against appropriate benchmarks.

On the other hand, hierarchical porosity may provoke unexpected effects on other zeolite properties like acidity. This effect has been realised in the case of ZSM-5 zeolite, a high silica material with mostly Brønsted acid sites when prepared in micron-size crystals. In contrast, as the mesopore/external surface area is increased in this zeolite due to the generation of a hierarchical porosity, an enhancement in the concentration of Lewis acid sites has been noted [125]. This effect is not just related to the formation of extra-framework Al species, i.e. they mainly originate from framework Al sites. This fact may also have important implications regarding catalytic activity and product selectivity in many reactions sensitive to the Brønsted/Lewis acid site ratios, but this has not been sufficiently addressed. In this way, a recent publication has pointed out that Lewis acidity in zeolites can be connected in many cases to Al framework species rather than to non-framework alumina (NFA), proposing the co-existence of various configurations for the former [126]. These findings evidence the need to gain further insights into Lewis acidity in zeolites, particularly in hierarchical zeolites, as it can play an important role in many catalytic applications.

Practically all known synthetic zeolites can be prepared to show hierarchical porosity features using many methods developed and applied in the literature to generate additional pores in the meso- and macropore ranges (Fig. 4) [99,100,103,110,127]. Among them are

post-synthesis treatments (top-down approach), such as destructive strategies based on removing framework atoms. This is the case for chemical or hydrothermal dealumination and chemical desilication, which may be preferentially applied to low- and high-silica zeolites, respectively. Ultrastable zeolite Y (USY), which is an essential component of industrial FCC catalysts, is prepared by hydrothermal extraction of Al species by controlled steaming, followed by acid treatment, thus leading to materials with a higher framework Si/Al ratio and enhanced stability while generating mesoporosity important for diffusion [128, 129].

The NFA (non-framework aluminium) generated by ultra-stabilization with steam dealumination maybe not be removed from the mesopores formed on ultrastabilization. Indeed, it contributes to the Lewis acidity of the catalyst and enhances the cracking of high molecular weight feed saturates and coke formation. When chemical dealumination is realized with hexafluorosilicic acid, the zeolite results ultrastabilized without forming mesopores containing NFA, leading to a significant reduction in catalytic activity but a great improvement in coke selectivity. Usually, however, the gain in the high MW conversion outweighed the coke selectivity improvement. This illustrates presence and benefit of mesopores containing NFA outweigh the negatives of not having them. It is possible to post-wash hydrothermally produced USY to remove NFA with dilute mineral acids. In such a case, the mesopores would be preserved while removing NFA. These USY samples with a high overall Si/Al ratio are commercially available. Still, the presence of NFA in the mesopores would enhance cracking activity towards high molecular weight feed, which is usually a preferable behaviour.

Likewise, diverse methods for preparing hierarchical zeolites are based on modifications in the crystallisation process (bottom-up approach), typically by incorporating an additional agent into the synthesis gel that acts as a mesoporegen [127]. Different types of surfactants, cationic polymers, silylated polymers, organosilanes and amphiphilic organosilanes should be highlighted among the many developed agents. Interestingly, several pioneering works on synthesising hierarchical zeolites using soft templates were published almost simultaneously [130–133]. Another strategy is to use hard templates, where zeolite crystallisation occurs within or around the hard template. In most cases, carbonaceous materials have been employed as hard

Fig. 4. Main strategies for the preparation of hierarchical zeolites.

templates [134], being carbon readily removed by calcination to generate additional porosity.

Interesting results have also been obtained when combining different synthesis strategies. One relevant example is the post-treatment of USY zeolite with basic surfactant-containing solutions under mild conditions [135,136], which has led to strong enhancement in the quality of the mesopores already present in the parent zeolite in terms of pore size uniformity and connectivity. The authors claim enhanced performance in the fluid catalytic cracking (FCC) processes. Another case that has been recently reported is the combination of pre-crystallization of ZSM-5 gel to promote the formation of protozeolitic nanounits, with the subsequent addition of amphiphilic organosilanes, followed by hydrothermal crystallization [137]. This treatment resulted in a zeolitic material possessing a dendritic nanoarchitecture consisting of a radially oriented pattern of branched nanounits. This material has exhibited enhanced adsorption properties and is claimed to improve catalytic activity in a variety of transformations when compared with nano- and hierarchical ZSM-5 samples, such as LDPE (low-density polyethylene) cracking, hydrogen production by methane decomposition and aldol condensation of furfural with cyclopentanone due to its outstanding accessibility and presence of a trimodal mesoporosity (Fig. 5). Nevertheless, the hydrothermal stability of zeolitic materials possessing a dendritic nanoarchitecture should be considered in case of their potential commercialization as industrial catalysts.

Catalytic cracking of polyolefinic plastics (LDPE, HDPE - high-density polyethylene - and PP - polypropylene) should, in principle, not be difficult as it proceeds under atmospheric pressure and at relatively mild temperatures below that corresponding to thermal decomposition (c.a. 400 °C), and high plastic/zeolite ratios [138].

Interestingly, recent work has reported that, by modulating micropore diffusion in ZSM-5 zeolite, polyethene cracking may proceed at temperatures as low as 280 °C in the presence of hydrogen with little coke formation, although with relatively high catalyst loadings [139]. Polyolefin cracking may occur on the external surface of zeolite crystals or pore mouth features without additional porosity (due to hierarchical structure), as in the case of nanocrystalline zeolites. The benefits of enhancing the intracrystalline zeolite activity are typically related to favouring the conversion of the cracked intermediates into valuable compounds, such as light olefins and aromatics [140,141]. The challenge with plastic cracking is not the cracking itself but the catalyst's tolerance to the diversity of contaminants (fillers, other polymers, chlorides, etc.) typically present in plastic wastes. Appropriate tolerance to such contaminants needs to be designed into the catalyst. Alternatively, pyrolysis oil derived from thermally cracked plastics can be fed to a catalytic reactor, thus avoiding the direct contact between the zeolite catalysts and many of the contaminants/poisons initially present in the raw plastic wastes.

Despite the huge amount of literature published during the past decades about synthesising hierarchical zeolites, several important issues besides those mentioned above still need to be addressed. Most of the work so far has been focused on aluminosilicate compositions. In contrast, the preparation of hierarchical zeolites incorporating other framework elements (such as Ga, Fe, Zr, Ti, Sn, etc.) has not yet been fully investigated. Progress in this direction may expand the application of hierarchical zeolites in important sectors, like environmental catalysis, the production of raw chemicals and the synthesis of sustainable jet fuels. In the same way, literature on the synthesis of pure silica hierarchical zeolites is relatively scarce, probably due to the softer interactions

Fig. 5. ZSM-5 zeolite with dendritic nanoarchitecture: a), b) TEM images, c) tomographic reconstruction cross-section, d) catalytic activity in LDPE cracking compared with nano- and hierarchical (non-dendritic) zeolite samples.

that may be established between silicate species and mesoprogen agents. However, hierarchical silica zeolites possess a strong potential for being used as supports of metal phases in high energy conditions due to their outstanding stability, deactivation resistance and regenerability, as recently highlighted in a review article [142]. Likewise, the benefits of incorporating metal phases within hierarchical zeolites have been assigned to synergistic effects derived from the encapsulation of metal nanoparticles in the confined spaces of the mesopores and the enhanced diffusion for reactants/intermediates/products [143].

Many of the synthesis strategies are quite difficult to scale-up to industrial capacities for various reasons (use of expensive reagents, complicated procedures, lack of reproducibility, etc.) that strongly hinder their economic feasibility, in addition to potentially strong environmental impacts that can be derived from several of these methods. Issues around emissions and effluent control, recovery and re-use of reagents, etc., have been typically not analyzed. In this way, a recent publication has reviewed the different methods so far employed for the preparation of hierarchical zeolites according to environmental aspects, identifying those routes that may fit better green synthesis concepts, such as solvent-free and template-free strategies and the use of alternative raw materials or green mesoprogen agents [144].

These important issues need to be addressed in a suitable way to enable the commercial deployment of hierarchical zeolites soon.

3. Rethinking catalytic zeolites from the perspective of future scenarios

The global zeolite market size was valued at USD 12.6 billion in 2021, with about 40% related to synthetic zeolites [145]. Forecasts for the zeolite market and future growth rate strongly depend on the scenario discussed, as commented in the introduction. In the short term, the compound annual growth rate (CAGR) is expected to increase, but with considerable regional variances associated with their different local regulations. In Europe, for example, due to the likely banning of light diesel engines (thus, also of catalytic converters for these cars), as commented in the introduction, reductions in biofuels and the closure of several refineries as well as the shrinkage of petrochemicals production, the market for zeolitic-type catalysts is expected to decline progressively. While there are positive market estimations (CAGR ~2–3%), they derive from the expansion of low-technology-level applications, such as

in the agriculture and detergent sectors, and environmental uses as adsorbents, from waste-water treatment to the purification and drying of gases. Fig. 6 summarises the synthetic zeolite market in 2021 by zeolite type and application [146].

About 30% of the market of synthetic zeolites (around \$5.3 billion in 2021) is due to catalytic applications. For this reason, there is a general effort to identify new market opportunities for zeolite as catalytic materials, even in the short term, to preserve the actual market and interest of the many companies in the sector. While top synthetic zeolite companies (BASF SE, Albemarle Co., Arkema, Clariant, CWK Chemiewerk Bad Köstritz GmbH, Honeywell International Inc., KNT Group, Tosoh Corporation, W. R. Grace & Co.-Conn., Zeolyst International) are often EU-based, the market will be progressively shifting out of EU. In addition, the increasing EU regulations regarding carbon footprint will further penalize the EU production of zeolites. Zeolite manufacturing processes are highly energy-intensive and have a significant carbon dioxide footprint [147]. Innovation in sustainable zeolite manufacturing and a push to develop higher added value zeolites for more sophisticated productions are thus two emerging needs for zeolite manufacture in Europe to preserve market perspectives. Nevertheless, due to the uncertain situation in the market and regulations, incentives to introduce new processes and catalysts that do not bring a large decrease to carbon footprint are limited, e.g., market perspectives shortly for just improved zeolitic catalysts (for example, hierarchically organised zeolites) are not positive.

It is useful to refer to different possible scenarios to analyse trends and perspectives for zeolites as catalysts and their emerging opportunities. Meng et al. [148] analysed pathways for transitioning the chemical industry, identifying three possible scenarios: i) a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, which is a low-carbon scenario with a still relevant role of fossil fuels, ii) a low circularity (LC) scenario to meet the carbon-neutral targets and iii) a high circularity (HC) scenario, which is a high-tech scenario with a high degree of substitution of fossil fuels (>70% in 2050). Fig. 7 reports the Sankey diagram for primary chemicals across different circularity scenarios [148]. It only refers to the scenarios for chemical production, to which the situation for the refining should be added to have the full impact on the zeolite market.

In the BAU scenario, the decrease in carbon footprint is mainly realised by i) increasing efficiency, ii) carbon capture and sequestration (CCS) technologies for both refinery and H₂ production processes, and

Fig. 6. Synthetic zeolite market in 2021 by zeolite type and application [146].

Fig. 7. Material demand changes (in Mt) of eight primary chemicals (ammonium nitrate and urea shown as part of ammonia) between 2020 and 2050 under LC, HC and BAU scenarios. Flow width indicates the masses of chemicals; flow colour is used to distinguish different types of chemicals; grey indicates the Business-as-usual (BAU) demand in 2020; red shows demand reduction through resource efficiency and circularity strategies, with improvements in agricultural practices included in the elimination wedge. Copyright, National Academy of Sciences 2023. Reproduced with permission from Meng et al. [148].

iii) a low degree of penetration of renewable energy resources, with thus still a dominant role of fossil fuels in the energy and chemical production (~75%). Chemical energy storage will be nearly absent (except for H₂), and there is limited growth in synthetic fuels and alternative feedstocks, such as liquefied plastic waste, instead of crude oil [149]. Target NZE emissions will not be reached in 2050. A decrease in GHG emissions will be realised mainly by an increase in the production of renewable energy sources, including uses in chemical production (electrification) and mobility.

In the LC and HC scenarios, the chemicals sector will be decoupled from fossil and switch to renewable carbon feedstocks. Carbon circularity will progressively dominate the landscape, with recycling, not only of material (plastics, etc.) but also of CO₂. CCS's role will decrease in favour of i) alternative greener production (for example, of H₂ and dependent processes such as ammonia) and ii) recycling of CO₂. Methanol to aromatics (MTX) will increase in relevance, and e-fuels and other energy vectors (ammonia, especially) will play a significant role. In the HC scenario, the chemical system passes NZE to become carbon emissions negative. More details can be found in ref. [150].

The cost of transition is a critical issue and one of the main points of discordance because the technology costs are widely influenced by many factors that are difficult to estimate precisely. McKinsey [151] indicates that a scenario to achieve net-zero emissions by around 2050 can be reached globally on a net-zero cost because an increase in costs in some areas would be compensated by saving in others. The Center for Global Commons [150] estimate that some chemicals, such as ammonia and methanol, will be competitive with actual production by 2050, while others, such as olefins and aromatics, could increase by 50–220% by 2050. Meng et al. [148] assume that, in general, the levelized production cost will almost double by 2050, although this will not translate to significantly higher costs for end-user products. In these estimations, it is assumed that the cost of production using current technologies will remain unchanged. On the contrary, this cost will likely increase more than double (as shortly discussed in the introduction) due to the change in the fossil fuel market and the social costs of their use. Thus, even if new low-carbon technologies have higher production costs, they will

likely still be “more economical” than those based on the actual routes at levelized costs translated to the effective 2050 scenario.

Table 1 reports an overview of the expected trends (for chemical production) and new process technologies (based on zeolites) for refinery and chemical production, which are expected according to the abovementioned scenarios. They are commented on later after introducing the status of zeolites from an industrial perspective and expected trends from this viewpoint.

3.1. Status of zeolites from an industrial perspective, with a focus on FCC and expected trends from this viewpoint

Today, the biggest zeolite demand in the world is FCC (fluid catalytic cracking), including around 350 ktpa (kilotons per annum) USY and ~15 ktpa ZSM-5 [152–154]. FCC is a very flexible process. Refiners are already looking into co-processing non-fossil fuels in the FCC along with the regular feedstock (examples: pyrolysis oils, bio-oils, and waste plastics) [155,156]. It is possible to adapt and modify the FCC to maximise olefins production [157–159] rather than gasoline or directly process crude oil to form chemicals [160,161]. This will require changes in the composition of the FCC catalysts. In addition, the FCC regenerator produces CO₂ (typically concentrated up to 18–19 vol%, balanced largely by nitrogen, but with some other trace gases that would need removing (SO_x, NO_x, O₂, and steam). Refiners are looking into options to re-purpose this CO₂-enriched source, e.g., methanol production or capture and sequester it in the worst case [149,162,163]. Zeolite catalysts, or adsorbents, will likely play a substantial role in these new applications [24,164–166].

Co-processing pyrolysis oils and waste plastics in the FCC is not trivial but is under serious investigation [167–170]. Amongst the new challenges are issues such as (1) deoxygenation of the co-feed, (2) dealing with new feed contaminants (e.g. fillers in waste plastics, Ca and K in biomass), (3) guiding the carbon and hydrogen towards incorporation into desired products as opposed losing it in the form of H₂O and CO₂ by-products. Early findings are that the amount of co-processed feeds is limited (up to 20% for easier bio-oils and less than <5% for

Table 1

Overview of the expected trends (for chemical production and refinery areas) and new zeolite-based technologies for refinery and chemical production according to possible scenarios up to 2050.

	<i>Low-carbon BAU scenario</i>	<i>LC scenario (most economic)</i>	<i>HC scenario</i>
<i>Expected trends</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction of fossil fuels use < 20% by 2050, NZE in chemical production not reached by 2050 2. Shift coal to natural gas (mainly for energy uses) 3. Minor changes in using renewable, low-carbon raw materials 4. Limited growth in synthetic fuels and alternative feedstocks, such as liquefied plastic waste 5. Low degree of penetration of renewable energy resources 6. Electrification of furnaces and reactors 7. CCS technologies for both refinery and H₂ production 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction of fossil fuels use 20–50% range by 2050, use of alternative C-sources 2. Reach NZE in chemical production around 2050, saving around 3 Gt global emissions 3. Low carbon circularity 4. Role of e-fuels and solar fuels limited to a specific area 5. Partial decoupling of the chemicals sector from fossil and limited switch to renewable carbon feedstocks 6. CCS's role will decrease 7. Introduction of processes using directly renewable energy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction of fossil fuels use > 50% by 2050, large use of alternative C-sources 2. Reach carbon-negative chemical production around 2050, saving about 12 Gt global emissions 3. High C-circularity, recycling not only of materials (plastics, etc.) but also of CO₂ 4. Significant impact (>10%) of e-fuels and solar fuels, large use of clean energy vectors 5. Large decoupling of the chemicals sector from fossil and a significant switch to renewable carbon feedstocks 6. Minimal role of CCS's technologies 7. Significant presence of processes using directly renewable energy
<i>New zeolite-based catalytic technologies for refinery</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consolidation of trends in moving refinery to chemical production 2. Novel zeolites for repurposing of FCCs 3. Catalysts for non-traditional FCC feedstocks, FCC co-processing, waste conversion 4. Novel technologies for aviation fuels or heavy transport 5. Multifunctional zeolitic materials, low sensitivity to contaminants 6. Producing H₂ from waste 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introducing new technologies for producing e-fuels, convert biogas, green H₂, CO₂ recycling. 2. Increase integration between refinery and chemical production 3. Decrease in use of zeolite in traditional refineries and biofuels, new opportunities for converting syngas and synthetic fuels 4. Production of carbon-neutral H₂ and derived energy vectors 5. CO₂ methanation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Signal change in the model of refineries, deep regional integration with local resources 2. Significant CO₂ recycling technologies 3. Large electrification of operations and reactors 4. Minor use of traditional refineries technologies and biofuel production 5. Novel technologies for producing synthetic fuels 6. Novel technologies to produce carbon neutral or negative H₂
<i>New zeolite-based catalytic technologies for chemical production</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New zeolite applications limited to fine and speciality chemicals 2. Modest increase in MTX technologies, tailored zeolites for MTO, limited growing of MTA 3. C2-C3 alcohol dehydration (from gas fermentation) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction of low-carbon raw materials (methanol, light olefins, aromatics) 2. Use of zeolites in technologies for converting biomass using renewable energy sources 3. Increasing use of MTX technologies, including for aromatics production 4. Alkanes upgrading using mono- and bifunctional microporous zeolite-type catalysts 5. Biomethane valorization 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Significant use (>30% in 2050) of low-carbon raw materials (methanol, light olefins, aromatics) 2. Start the use of zeolite-modified electrodes and electrode-modified zeolites represent, MOF-type conductive electrodes or ZTC 3. Over 30% of raw materials derived by MTX technologies in 2050 4. Introduction of hybrid catalysts for one-stage conversion of CO₂ 5. Cascade processes for fine chemicals

more challenging pyrolysis oils). Increased usage of ZSM-5 can improve product yields and properties when co-processing. So, as the trend progresses, there will likely be a partial shift from USY towards more sophisticated zeolites, like ZSM-5 and others that have yet to be tried in this very new application area. Successful zeolitic materials should have good hydrothermal stability, ideally exhibit 3-dimensional micropore diffusion, moderately high acid site density, and potential sites that can anchor catalytically active metals (e.g. silanol nests) that can activate new functionalities for the new feeds [171].

Another example of FCC re-purposing is the shift from "fuels" to "chemicals" orientation [172–174]. Today, ZSM-5 is a part of the regular catalyst diet in many standard FCC units. ZSM-5 cracks (unwanted) gasoline into light olefins that can be used in petrochemical applications [175], e.g. propylene monomer for polypropylene production. New generations of FCC units are being built, purpose-made for petrochemicals production [176], e.g.: (1) installation of a second riser dedicated to alternate feedstocks – allowing complete segregation of the co-feed, which usually requires different operating conditions than the standard feed going to the primary riser: for example higher RXT (e.g. ~600 °C vs ~530 °C), cat/oil ratio (e.g. 15–20 vs 5–7) for a naphtha cracking riser; (2) pure naphtha cracking, employing very different catalysts to conventional FCC (e.g. modified ZSM-5 based catalysts and often little or no USY at all); and (3) pure biomass catalytic fast pyrolysis also requiring a fully different zeolite-based catalyst system.

The amount of ZSM-5 being used in FCCs has been growing strongly [154,177] and is projected to continue growing. Five new FCC projects, focused on chemical products in India alone [178], are expected to increase ZSM-5 demand by over 20% globally. There is no doubt that ZSM-5 is becoming more important. ZSM-5-based catalysts pop-up in

many emerging industrial applications: FCC and future forms may evolve into methanol to olefins, fast catalytic pyrolysis, cracking of waste plastics, aromatics production and separation, and other uses.

3.2. Emerging catalytic applications in a low-carbon BAU scenario with a continued significant role for fossil fuels

3.2.1. Expected trends

In this scenario, it is expected that the use of fossil fuels as a carbon source for chemical production will remain essentially constant up to 2050, balancing, from one side, increases in demand for fuels and chemicals and, from the other side, increases in efficiency (reduction and recycling of waste, increased energy efficiency) and electrification of chemical processes, that lead to the continued requirement for fossil fuels. On the other hand, coal use will decrease in favour of natural gas [179,180], although especially as an energy source.

No major changes will occur in the raw materials for chemical production using renewable, low-carbon raw materials. The use of biomass sources will remain secondary. Innovation in new zeolite applications will be limited to small areas, such as fine and speciality chemicals, with lower investment risks. A modest increase in MTX technologies (to produce olefins from non-fossil fuels via methanol) is expected. In the refinery, the situation will largely depend on geographical areas.

In Europe, a contraction of production is expected and, thus, limited incentives to develop novel processes if not to comply with regulations or focus on sectors such as aviation fuels or heavy transport, where electrifying mobility will be ineffective. A modest increase in the use of alternative carbon sources, such as biomass and waste, is expected. Due to the lower revenues from traditional products, such as gasoline, diesel

and heating fuels, refineries must adapt to shifting demand by capturing requests for petrochemical feedstocks [174]. Thus, developing solutions for refining crude into chemicals will become more important.

3.2.2. New zeolite-based catalytic technologies for refinery

Section 4.1 has already commented on the status and perspectives of FCC in the conservative scenario discussed in this section, which often coincides with the industrial viewpoint. The main trend is the repurposing of FCCs to produce much higher petrochemical yields or directly convert crude to olefins [161]. Among the developmental strategies used to achieve this goal are: i) controlling extra-framework alumina, ii) developing novel zeolite which combines small pores to enhance olefin formation with large pores to allow fast diffusion of bulky molecules while preserving thermal stability, including during regeneration, iii) crystal engineering to maximise catalytic effectiveness, iv) using hard template methods to control mesoporosity, v) developing micro-/mesoporous zeolite composites, vi) introduction of heteroatoms to improve stability, vii) tuning Al siting and distribution during synthesis and viii) polysynthetic methods, such as zoning and surface passivation, to improve performance and stability [159,181]. Some of these issues are discussed *vide supra*.

In on-purpose-olefins designed FCC units, olefins yields are maximised by adjusting catalysts, operations, and unit design. However, they essentially retain many of the features of conventional FCC technology. In processing light feedstocks, the use of non-traditional FCC feedstocks, such as light straight-run naphtha (LSN), straight-run naphtha (SRN), natural gas condensates and wild-naphthas, light coker naphtha (LKN), and/or heavy coker naphtha (HKN), and other light streams (methanol, mixed C4, mixed C5) is also emerging. Medium-pore zeolites (usually ZSM-5) are required to crack these low MW feed molecules at high steam dilution and high reactor temperatures to maximise olefin selectivity.

Zeolites for these applications, vs standard FCC, vary from i) a mixture of low RE-USY zeolite (0–0.5 wt% RE) as the main catalyst (lower RE to decrease hydrogen transfer selectivity and thereby preserve

olefins selectivity) together with a ZSM-5 containing co-catalyst (or additive), to ii) the use of 100% ZSM-5 based catalysts, without a RE-USY catalyst at all; in either case use of ZSM-5 becomes essential to achieve high light olefin yields.

FCC co-processing (pyrolysis oils, bio-oils, waste plastics) [167,182] and dedicated catalytic processes for waste conversion (e.g. fast catalytic pyrolysis, cracking pyrolysis vapours, plastics, etc.) [18,114,183,184] were already commented before. Lee et al. [185] recently proposed a unified view on biomass and waste plastics catalytic conversion, summarised in Table 2.

Multifunctional zeolitic materials should be developed to optimise performance. The cleavage of C_{aliph}-C bonds may benefit from the extensive refinery experience. In addition to dealing with high levels of contaminants (e.g. Ca, K, Mg, etc.) and the very high oxygen content of biomass (usually over 40% of biomass by weight), an issue common with pyrolysis oils is avoiding polymerisation reactions at moderate temperatures, which requires design-specific storage and feed injection strategies as well as reactor design.

Producing H₂ from waste [186–189] is another emerging area in this scenario, although the carbon footprint is still significantly higher than green H₂ [187], similar to the processes of waste-to-fuel discussed above. Thus, only in a scenario like that commented on in this section will these processes play a significant role, even if waste disposal still has to be realised. However, recycling and greener options must be preferred in LC and HC scenarios.

3.2.3. New zeolite-based catalytic technologies for chemical production

In the discussed scenario, the only area with significant growing demand for tailored zeolite is the methanol to olefins (MTO) process, where methanol will mainly come from fossil fuels, but also, to a lesser extent, derived from biogenic resources and CO₂ conversion. However, olefins will still mainly be produced by the traditional routes. Methanol to aromatics (MTA) is not expected to be a significant route because refineries will continue to produce sufficient aromatics. To a small

Table 2

Summary of catalytic conversion of various plastic and biomass substrates via activating C–C, C–O and C–N bonds. PA, polyamide; PC, polycarbonate; PET, polyethylene terephthalate; PPO, poly(p-phenylene oxide); PU, polyurethane. Reproduced with permission from ref. [18]. Copyright Nature Group, 2022.

Bonds	Feedstocks	Methods	Catalysts	Products		
C–C	C _{aliph} –C _{aliph}	Ubiquitous in biomass and plastic	Catalytic cracking	Brønsted acid	Alkanes, light olefins and bio-oils	
		C _{arom} –C _{aliph}	Lignin fragments featuring β–5, β–1, β–β and α–1 linkages, PS, PC and PF	Hydrogenolysis	Metal	Paraffins and aromatics
				Hydrocracking	Metal–acid	iso-Paraffins
	Metathesis (requiring C=C bond)			Homogeneous and heterogeneous metathesis catalysts	Hydrocarbons	
C _{arom} –C _{arom}	Lignin fragments featuring 5–5' linkages	Retro-aldol reaction (requiring β-hydroxy carbonyl unit)	Metal–Lewis acid	Polyols and alcohols		
		Catalytic cracking	Brønsted acid	Aromatics and phenolics		
		Reductive cleavage	Metal and metal–acid	Aromatics, cycloalkanes and phenolics		
C–O	Ether bond	Cellulose, chitin, lignin, epoxy resins and PPO	Oxidation–hydrogenation (requiring β–O–4 linkages)	Combination of metal and oxidant	Phenol	
			Reductive cleavage	Homogeneous and heterogeneous metal catalysts and metal–acid	Phenolics	
	Ester bond	Triglyceride, PET and PC	Reductive cleavage using H ₂	Metal and metal–acid	Phenolics, aromatics and cycloalkanes	
			Reductive cleavage using other reagents (for example, amine, organosilane and LiAlH ₄)	Metal	Phenolics and N-containing chemicals	
C–N	Amide bond	Protein, PA and PU	Oxidative Hydrolysis (requiring a glycosidic bond)	Acid, base and metal-organic	Aromatic oxygenated chemicals	
			Solvvolysis	Metal halides and acid	Carbohydrates	
C–N	Amide bond	Protein, PA and PU	Hydrolysis (requiring a glycosidic bond)	Acid, base, metal halides and acetates	Alcohol and carboxylic acids	
			Solvvolysis	Metal and metal–acid	Alcohol, carboxylic acids and hydrocarbons	
C–N	Amide bond	Protein, PA and PU	Hydrogenolysis	Strong acid, strong base and transition metal salts	Amino acids and aliphatic ester/aminocaproic acid	
			Hydrogenolysis	Metal and metal-centred pincer catalysts	Amides, amino alcohols and polyols	

extent, ethylene will be produced from bioethanol but via gas fermentation [190,191] rather than conventional fermentation routes. Isopropanol, and thus propylene by dehydration, could also be produced by gas fermentation. Although the dehydration of zeolites is well established, milder acidic zeolites with higher activity must be developed [26]. Some impurities in alcohols from gas fermentation are not present in conventional fermentation. Hence their possible effect requires attention.

In this scenario, minimal novel processes for producing chemicals from biomass are expected due to their low cost-effectiveness in reducing the carbon footprint and the limited incentives in introducing novel processes. The transformation of biomass into valuable products is hindered by several factors, such as its complex composition and the need for multiple steps, severe conditions and costly separations for their utilisation. The engineering of zeolitic materials has made giant progress in the last decades for biomass valorisation [36]. They will not be the limiting factor to the large-scale application of these processes. R&D activities in the zeolite area, particularly multifunctional materials, would be instead necessary for fine and speciality chemicals [192–194].

3.3. Emerging catalytic applications in a carbon-neutral or -negative scenario with low or high circularity, respectively (LC or HC)

3.3.1. Expected trends

These scenarios require substituting significantly (up to 70%) fossil fuels with renewable energy and alternative C-sources. They differ in terms of the degree of substitution, timing to reach NZE or even carbon-negative emission (for the chemical production sector) and degree of circularity. The LC scenario (intermediate between the low-carbon BAU and HC scenarios) is the most economical of the three considered [150]. It will save (for the chemical sector) about 3 Gt global emissions. The HC scenario can save up to 12 Gt global emissions but at a much higher cost. The LC scenario is thus the most likely.

3.3.2. New zeolite-based catalytic technologies for refinery

In the energy sector, decreasing GHG emissions requires combining many emerging technologies: i) fuel switching to biomass, synthetic fuels (e-fuels), and biogas from waste, ii) CO₂ recycling using renewable energy sources, iii) larger introduction of electrified technologies, iv) green H₂ from electrolysis to other technologies, including biomethane cracking, v) production of alternative energy vectors to those derived from fossil fuels and vi) energy efficiency [195]. A transformation to the model for refinery development is expected due to the cost growth of refining, the pressure on margins ramps up, and major changes in the market. Of the possible future refineries models (global competitors, regional champions, and new energy platforms), deep regional integration with local resources will likely be the winning solution.

The role of zeolitic materials has to be considered from this perspective. The use of zeolitic materials for traditional refinery applications (FCC, hydrocracking, isomerisation) will decrease, as well as the production of biofuels, depending largely on geographical area and related political decisions. e-Fuels (and solar fuels, where the difference is related to whether the H₂ is produced separately or integrated into the process, as in the second case) will also be limited to heavy transport and aviation, but with an increasing role of synthetic fuels (>30%) in HC scenario. This creates opportunities for zeolites in i) hybrid catalysts to convert syngas (from non-fossil sources), ii) hydroconversion of hydrocarbons obtained through Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, iii) producing jet fuels from bioethanol, other bio-based fractions or waste, and iv) via ethylene oligomerisation [196–201]. The main challenge is that a large distribution of hydrocarbon fractions is obtained in traditional processes but with high separation costs, affordable for large-scale plants and using all the fractions. In contrast, these distributed applications require maximising the formation of only aviation or diesel for heavy transport cuts because the others, such as gasoline, will have minor value because of the discussed restructuring of the market. Thus, new selective zeolitic

materials need to be developed [202].

Opportunities also are present to produce valuable hydrocarbon cuts directly from CO₂ (CO₂-to-jet-fuel [203]) or syngas, which may derive from different sources (waste, etc.) and thus may contain different impurities. Among the relevant energy vectors is methane, the so-called power-to-gas process, where excess renewable energy is stored as a chemical vector. Metallozeolites offer relevant opportunities for improving catalysts for CO₂ methanation [204]. Hydrophobicity is one of the crucial aspects to optimise the behaviour in CO₂ methanation because water inhibition can severely impact the reaction. Another important characteristic is metallic hydrogenating components' creation, dispersion, and high stability.

3.3.3. New zeolite-based catalytic technologies for chemical production

In this area, the main efforts will be i) producing low-carbon raw materials (methanol, light olefins, aromatics) and ii) use of renewable energy directly to drive the chemical processes, thus moving toward technologies such as electrocatalysis [32,33,205]. Zeolite-like electrodes are an interesting concept [206], although zeolitic materials are not conductive. However, it is possible to develop MOF-type conductive electrodes [207–209] or zeolite-templated carbon (ZTC) [210–212] electrodes.

Still used mainly as electrodes in batteries and energy-storage devices, these materials offer great opportunities to develop next-generation selective electrocatalysts for a range of electrocatalytic reactions relevant to carbon-neutral chemical production. They offer unique possibilities to stabilise unusual nanoclusters or metal complexes within a host-ordered matrix, control the transport of molecules to them, and induce changes in the reactivity due to confinement [213]. In addition, they are very interesting electrode substrates for realizing hybrid bioelectrodes [214].

Production of olefins and aromatics from fossil fuels via traditional processes will progressively decrease in favour of new technology, MTX process primarily (starting from non-fossil fuel carbon sources), but in the longer term also via direct electrocatalytic processes [32,33]. While methanol (or dimethyl ether) conversion to olefins (MTO) or selectively propylene (MTP) or aromatics (MTA) are well-established processes and with established catalysts [215–217], improvement to reduce deactivation and improve selectivity are still necessary. Realising hybrid catalysts for one-stage conversion of CO₂ is also an active area of research [218–220], although the effective advantages are not yet fully proven.

Alkane upgrading using mono- and bifunctional microporous zeolite-type catalysts [221] is another area of potential relevance for producing alternative raw materials for chemical production. Methane can be converted via oxidative and non-oxidative routes and even carboxylated by CO₂ to acetic acid. Light alkanes (C₂–C₄) can be converted to olefins or other chemicals, including aromatics. Methane conversion into higher-value chemicals is the most attractive but ambitious objective, still mainly at the possibility level. Light alkanes conversion is more feasible but still to be developed [221]. Isolated or single-atom species or subnanometric metal clusters in zeolite are among the promising catalysts for these new applications. The use of metallo zeolite-based catalysts in these novel processes brings relevant benefits.

Many advances in zeolite science and technology, among them the precise control of active guest sites and the framework topologies that allow tuning the nanoconfinement effects, acid sites and their location, the secondary-pore systems, extraframework cations and atoms, hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity, and proximity between active sites, allow expanding the application of zeolites to C1 chemistry [222]. The many uses of zeolites in C1 chemistry are summarised in Fig. 8.

Although discussion is limited here to zeolites as catalysts, they will also play a relevant role as selective sorbents or membrane components in future refineries and chemical plants [164,223,224].

Advanced zeolites will also be relevant in converting CO₂ to chemicals and fuels [24] in the scenarios discussed. See also Table 2. A scheme of the various possibilities, discussed in detail by Velty and

CO Conversion		Reaction conditions & Catalysts
FT synthesis	$\text{CO} + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{M}} \text{C}_n\text{H}_m \text{ intermediates} \xrightarrow{\text{Z}} \text{Hydrocarbons}$	230-400°C, $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}=1-2$, 1-2 Mpa, <i>Fe, Co, Ru/ZSM-5</i>
Methanol/DME-mediated	$\text{CO} + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{M}} \text{CH}_3\text{OH/DME} \xrightarrow{\text{Z}} \text{Hydrocarbons}$	300-400°C, $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}=1-2$, 2-4 Mpa, <i>ZnZrO₂/SAPO-34</i>
Methanol/DME-mediated	$\text{CO} + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{M}} \text{CH}_3\text{OH/DME} \xrightarrow{\text{ZM}} \text{Higher Alcohols}$	200-300°C, $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}=1-2$, 3-5 Mpa, <i>CuZnAl/Mordenite</i>
CO ₂ Conversion		
Modified FT synthesis	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{M}} \text{CO} + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{ZM}} \text{Hydrocarbons}$	300-350°C, $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2=2-3$, 2-4 Mpa, <i>Fe₃O₄/ZSM-5</i>
Methanol/DME-mediated	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{M}} \text{CH}_3\text{OH/DME} \xrightarrow{\text{Z}} \text{Hydrocarbons}$	300-400°C, $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2=3$, 3 Mpa, <i>In₂O₃-ZnO₂/SAPO-34</i>
Methanol-mediated	$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{M}} \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \xrightarrow{\text{Z}} \text{DME}$	200-300°C, $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2=2-3$, 3 Mpa, <i>CuZnZr-based/ZSM-5</i>
CH ₄ Conversion		
CH ₄ to methanol	$\text{CH}_4 + \text{O}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{ZM}} \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	70-200°C, $\text{CH}_4/\text{N}_2=19$, 5000 mL-g _{cat} ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹ , <i>Fe, Cu/Mordenite</i>
CH ₄ to aromatic	$\text{CH}_4 \xrightarrow{\text{ZM}} \text{Aromatics}$	700°C, $\text{CH}_4/\text{N}_2=9$, 1500 mL-g _{cat} ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹ , <i>Mo/ZSM-5</i>
CH ₃ OH Conversion		
MTO reaction	$\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \xrightarrow{\text{Z}} \text{Olefins (ethylene and propylene)}$	400-450°C, WHSV= 2-4 h ⁻¹ , <i>SAPO-34</i>
MTP reaction	$\text{CH}_3\text{OH} \xrightarrow{\text{Z}} \text{Propylene}$	450-500°C, WHSV= 3-10 h ⁻¹ , <i>ZSM-5</i>
HCOOH Conversion		
Dehydrogenation reaction	$\text{HCOOH} \xrightarrow{\text{ZM}} \text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2$	25-60°C, ambient atmosphere, <i>Pd@silicalite-1</i>

M Metallic species
Z Zeolite catalysts/supports (hydrocracking, isomerization, aromatization, carbonylation, alkylation, dehydration, etc.)

Fig. 8. Summary of representative routes from C1 molecules to value-added chemicals and corresponding most-studied catalysts and reaction conditions. Copyright, Wiley 2020.

Elaborated with permission from Zhang et al. [222].

Corma [24], is presented in Fig. 9. Although only part of these reactions will have the practical possibility of implementation, due to still low performances, the presence of better alternatives and high costs, the Figure illustrates well the range of possibilities offered by engineered zeolitic materials to address future challenges.

Other examples discussed by Yu et al. [12,225,226] are i) zeolite-encapsulated Rh single-atom for H₂ production from ammonia-borane or formic acid decomposition and ii) propylene production by propane dehydrogenation using bimetallic Pt-Zn catalysts encapsulated inside silicalite-1 zeolite. As emerging directions, they indicate i) the hydrogenation reactions of CO/CO₂, unsaturated compounds, and nitrogenous compounds and ii) the oxidation of CO,

methane, and alkene.

These examples show that zeolites will still play an important role in future energy and chemical production. The knowledge of their synthesis, tuning and engineering will be the key factor for opening new directions. Several of them should be further developed before arriving at an actual application, and their development should be considered concerning the evolving scenario, briefly discussed in this contribution. For various uses, even indicated as emerging directions, market demands will be different, and they will not be applied. On the other hand, new fields, such as electrodes with an ordered pore structure, which have been only scarcely investigated, have the potential to become crucial in emerging new processes.

Fig. 9. Scheme of CO₂ conversion to valuable chemicals and fuels using zeolite- and OPM-based catalysts. Copyright, RSC 2023. Elaborated with permission from Velty and Corma [24].

4. Conclusions and recommendations

Catalysis with zeolites is facing significant challenges due to the energy transition [227]. This perspective article summarizes the authors' joint view on future directions in zeolite chemistry and catalytic applications, even without being exhaustive for conciseness. The particular challenges discussed here include i) our view of the zeolite synthesis focused on new structures with optimised textural properties and design of zeolite catalysts with precise control of the location of active sites, ii) discussion of current but mostly new industrial demands of zeolites, and iii) emerging catalytic application, in which zeolites should play a key role and last but not least opportunities for new types of microporous solids.

Zeolites are a unique class of catalytic materials because their characteristics and the possibility of fine-tuning by precise synthesis combined with advanced characterization and modelling allow a high level of design for various catalytic applications. Nevertheless, there are still many challenges in their fundamental understanding and design. These challenges were shortly discussed in Section 2 regarding (i) the precise synthesis and control of location and type of acid sites and (ii) the opportunities for new types and textures of zeolites. Zeolites offer many opportunities and advances for heterogeneous catalysts: precise control of the structure and porosity, controlled location of active sites, and more.

Nevertheless this great potential, their future is uncertain. A deep transition is occurring, with major changes in the energy and raw materials and a drastic modification of the nexus between the refinery and chemical production based on the current large deployment of zeolites as catalysts. This contribution thus attempted to analyze and discuss the role of zeolite in a future sustainable, low-carbon, energy and chemical production scenario. Being very difficult to predict what the scenario realized up to 2050 will be, we have organized the discussion along three possible scenarios based on literature indications: (i) a low-carbon BAU scenario and (ii) two advanced scenarios (LC and HC), which differ in terms of a low and high degree of circularity (LC and HC, respectively) and level of substitution of fossil fuels with alternative energy and carbon sources. Although there are assumptions in each of these scenarios, and it is difficult to precisely predict which will be applied and whether each of the assumptions will be realized, this exercise provides indications to the readers to derive his/her vision of the future and related priorities in catalysis by zeolites. As a summary, Table 1 provides an overview of the expected trends and impact on zeolite in these scenarios.

It is evident that together with a long-term vision (2050 and beyond), it is necessary to implement a progressive transition and create the economic conditions to make this feasible. It is not the place here to discuss these aspects. However, history teaches that when deep transitions occur, strong synergic aspects "catalyze" and accelerate the transformation, while underestimated factors become crucial. We shortly discussed the cost of fossil fuels when some current uses would no longer be present. This will likely cause a strong increase in their cost that, together with the increasing need for energy and raw materials security, will accelerate the transition to a potentially fossil-free future and a transformation from a centralized to a distributed production model. This has major consequences on the type of catalytic technologies required to enable this change and, thus, the need for zeolite in future sustainable production.

Nevertheless, the analysis provided and summarized in Table 1, even if some aspects maybe not be shared by all, indicates that zeolitic-type materials will still play a considerable role in the future of chemical production [228]. This is due to the great advances in their synthesis and understanding outlined in Section 2. Although today the number of zeolites in industrial use is limited to less than ten, as shown in Fig. 6, despite the much higher number of zeo-type materials, the great advances in a design tailored zeolitic materials will be the key to make faster their adaptation to the new demands and reactions due to this deep transition.

Our final recommendation is thus that innovation in catalysis science and technology derives from combining the capability of an in-depth understanding, a precise synthesis and the capability to predict in advance what will be the requests for future industrial use. We have outlined our indications, summarized in Table 1, but it is important to remark that each researcher must develop his/her vision, avoiding accepting uncritical literature or other indications. Within the limit possible in a critical review, we hope to have provided the elements, tools and clues to allow each reader to identify his/her priorities in the research and application of zeolite catalysts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

All authors contributed equally in preparing and revising the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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